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Technical note on spectral calibration

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>Calibration of the spectral axis is investigated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A new, fast model to calibrate the spectral axis for CAIRT limb-observations is used (1) show that even for errors in the spectral axis of 0.3 cm^{-1} (i.e. 420-140 ppm from 720 to 2200 cm^{-1}), the model is capable to derive the spectral correction with an error of a few ppm, and (2) to investigate which wavenumber/tangent altitude ranges are best suited for spectral calibration with this model. - Level-2 1d-retrieval uncertainty analysis for 2 ppm spectral uncertainty is performed indicating that a shift-uncertainty of 2 ppm seem adequate for many L-2 retrieval targets as a threshold value for spectral calibration. 		
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Table of Content

1.	Introduction	5
2.	Spectral shift determination for CAIRT: new model	5
3.	Spectral shift determination for CAIRT: results	5
4.	Spectral shift determination for CAIRT: conclusions	6
5.	Level-2 1d-retrieval results for 2 ppm spectral uncertainty	6

List of figures

Figure 1	Altitude-dependent uncertainty of the spectral calibration for windows each of width 5 cm^{-1} along the whole spectral range of CAIRT. Top: no noise applied; bottom threshold noise values applied; in between: noise reduces by a factor of 1/16 and 1/4. Measurement-atmosphere: April+45_day, test-atmosphere: April+45_day	7
Figure 2	same as Figure 1 but measurement-atmosphere: April+00_day, test-atmosphere: April+45_day. ..	8
Figure 3	same as Figure 1 but measurement-atmosphere: July-80_night, test-atmosphere: April+45_day. ..	9
Figure 4	same as Figure 1 but measurement-atmosphere: July+80_day, test-atmosphere: April+45_day. ...	10
Figure 5	Vertical profiles of estimated retrieval errors relative to L2-threshold values due to wavenumber calibration uncertainties of 2 ppm. Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the related altitude regions. Different columns indicate different spectral window datasets used in the retrieval. Empty figures are due to non-present window collections.....	11
Figure 6	Same as Figure 5 for other retrieval targets.....	12
Figure 7	Same as Figure 5 for other retrieval targets.....	13
Figure 8	Same as Figure 5 for other retrieval targets.....	14

1. Introduction

Calibration of the spectral axis is investigated.

2. Spectral shift determination for CAIRT: new model

In this chapter, a newly developed (fast) model to calibrate the spectral axis for CAIRT limb-observations is used to:

- show that even for errors in the spectral axis of 0.3 cm^{-1} (i.e. 420-140 ppm from 720 to 2200 cm^{-1}), the model is capable to derive the spectral correction with an error of a few ppm
- investigate which wavenumber/tangent altitude ranges are best suited for spectral calibration with this model

The model works as follows:

- so-called 'monochromatic' broad-band limb-spectra with a sampling of 0.0001 cm^{-1} have been calculated for different atmosphere from the ERS climatology
- the April+45_day monochromatic limb-radiances are used as the 'test' cases against which other 'measured' spectra are compared (correlated)
- in spectral windows of 5 cm^{-1} width, the monochromatic (0.0001 cm^{-1}) radiances are convolved with a Norton-Beer Strong function to simulate a measurement of an interferometer of 2.5 cm MOPD. This means the resulting 'measured' spectra have a sample distance of 0.2 cm^{-1} .
- to these 'measurements' a certain amount of noise is added (from no-noise to the threshold-wavenumber-dependent noise value).
- the resulting 'noisy measurements' of different atmospheres are tested against the April+45_day radiances by shifting these test-spectra over the 'measured' spectra in steps of 0.0001 cm^{-1} from -0.3 to $+0.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at each step recording the RMSD (root mean square deviation).
- the result of the 'retrieval' is the position where the RMSD reaches a minimum.

3. Spectral shift determination for CAIRT: results

Figure 1 to Figure 4 show the altitude- and wavenumber-dependent results of the uncertainty of spectral calibration using the model described above.

- Figure 1, top row: shows the 'ideal' result: the 'measurement' atmosphere is equal to the 'test' dataset (April+45_day) and no noise (Noise factor = 0.0) has been applied. This demonstrates that for the ideal case the model delivers a 'perfect' result over all tangent altitudes and wavenumbers.
- Figure 1, rows 2-4: application of noise to the 'measured' spectra increases the uncertainty of the spectral calibration. The quality of the retrieval increases towards lower altitudes as well as with reduction of the noise value (as printed in the title of each sub-plot). However, also at single acquisition noise level (Noise factor = 1), there are still windows scattered along the wavenumber axis where an accuracy of $< 2 \text{ ppm}$ can be achieved.
- Figure 2 - Figure 4, top row: show the performance of using the 'test' atmospheric simulated radiances of April+45_day to perform spectral calibration of measurements under different atmospheric conditions. Though there are spectral windows/heights which are not suited any more, still many windows remain where a spectral calibration resulting in uncertainties below 2 ppm seem possible.
- Figure 2 - Figure 4, rows 2-4: with some deterioration, the same as said above for the April+45_day measurement remains valid. The most difficult case here is the Antarctic winter atmosphere (Figure 3).

4. Spectral shift determination for CAIRT: conclusions

- Even with a relatively easy and straight-forward fast model, a converging spectral fit starting with a large error (0.3 cm⁻¹) is possible
- The quality of the wavenumber-calibration increases strongly with temporal averaging.
- Above about 50 km, only very few windows allow for a good fit of better than 2 ppm.
- Best fits with possible windows scattered over the whole wavelength range are reached between 20 and 50 km of tangent altitude.

5. Level-2 1d-retrieval results for 2 ppm spectral uncertainty

Figure 5 to Figure 8 show retrieval results for a one-dimensional profile retrieval approach for the CAIRT target species and four different sets of altitude-dependent microwindows.

The following baselines have been applied:

- **1d-linear profile retrieval**
- **All ERS atmospheres**
- Error spectra for 2 ppm wavenumber shift uncertainty.
- **Vertical resolution** profiles are prescribed as defined in the **MATER L2-requirements** by adapting the vertical retrieval grid accordingly. **Threshold vertical resolution** is applied here throughout.
- In addition to the **CAIRT baseline microwindow set ('CAIRTstd'** as used in the D8 and D10 reports for 2d LPE error analysis and retrieval exercises in SciReC), three more microwindow sets have been explored (for plots of the different microwindow sets: see e.g. appendix in Technical Note on elevation jitter.)
- The resulting altitude-dependent errors are plotted **relative to the requirement thresholds**.

Results:

- In general, for species with broad-band spectral features, like the CFCs, N₂O₅, PAN, H₂SO₄, the retrieval error due to spectral uncertainties is negligible
- Species with more located features, the wavenumber-shift uncertainty introduces often larger retrieval errors and depend strongly on the set of chosen spectral windows (e.g. H₂O).
- Largest errors of up to 20% of the requirement threshold values in the different altitude regions appear in case of temperature, H₂O, O₃ and NO₂-retrievals.
- These results indicate that a shift-uncertainty of 2 ppm seem adequate as a threshold value for spectral calibration and should be taken into consideration as an error source.

Figure 1 Altitude-dependent uncertainty of the spectral calibration for windows each of width 5 cm^{-1} along the whole spectral range of CAIRT. Top: no noise applied; bottom threshold noise values applied; in between: noise reduces by a factor of 1/16 and 1/4. Measurement-atmosphere: April+45_day, test-atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 2 same as Figure 1 but measurement-atmosphere: April+00_day, test-atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 3 same as Figure 1 but measurement-atmosphere: July-80_night, test-atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 4 same as Figure 1 but measurement-atmosphere: July+80_day, test-atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 5 Vertical profiles of estimated retrieval errors relative to L2-threshold values due to wavenumber calibration uncertainties of 2 ppm. Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the

related altitude regions. Different columns indicate different spectral window datasets used in the retrieval. Empty figures are due to non-present window collections.

Figure 6 Same as Figure 5 for other retrieval targets.

Figure 7 Same as Figure 5 for other retrieval targets.

Figure 8 Same as Figure 5 for other retrieval targets.